

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

Grant agreement ID: 101091268

Preliminary version on decision support tool for soil health business models

Deliverable D 3.6

Project	NOVASOIL
Project title	INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
Work Package	3 Testing and development of a toolbox for incentives
Deliverable	3.6
Period covered	01/11/2022-07/07/2024
Publication date	29/07/2024
Dissemination level	PU
Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this report	New Bulgarian University
Authors	Dimitre Nikolov, Ekatherina Tzvetanova-Georgieva, Ivan Boevsky, Martin Banov, Krasimir Kostenarov, Kristina Todorova
Contributors	

QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

This document has been reviewed according to the NOVASOIL Project Management Plan.

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	22/07/2024	NBU	Draft version circulated by email
2	V2.0	22/07/2024	EVENOR	First reactions and comments
3	V3.0	30/07/2024	NBU	Final version
4	V3.1	31/07/2024	EVENOR	Minor changes

Project Consortium

N°	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	GE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	GE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGEEESTI	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

Table of contents

List of figures	7
List of tables	7
List of abbreviations	8
Summary	9
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Context of WP 3 objectives	9
1.2 Connection with the other WPs	9
1.3 Purpose and scope of the document	10
1.4 Process of development	10
2 Conceptual framework	11
2.1 DST framework and connection between the tools	12
2.2 NOVASOIL DST description	12
2.2.1 Registration module	13
2.2.2 Risk assessment module (RAM)	14
2.2.3 Optimisation module	20
3 Design of the DTs	25
3.1 Registration module	25
3.2 Risk assessment module	26
3.3 Optimisation module	30
4 Conclusions	32
Resources	34
Acknowledgment	35

List of figures

Figure 1. WP 3 digital toolbox.....	12
Figure 2. NOVASOIL DST connection.....	12
Figure 3. HOVASOIL DSTs architecture	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
Figure 4. NOVASOIL DST home page.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
Figure 5 RAM first page	26
Figure 6 RAM soil L-level.....	26
Figure 7 RAM - predominant slope.....	27
Figure 8 RAM – stony layer	27
Figure 9 RAM - groundwater level.....	28
Figure 10 RAM - root zone	28
Figure 11 RAM - Soil pH	29
Figure 12 RAM - result	29
Figure 13 RAM recommendations.....	29
Figure 14 Risk assessment module – first screen	30
Figure 15 Risk assessment module – second screen.....	31
Figure 16 Risk assessment module – third screen	31
Figure 17 Risk assessment module – fourth screen.....	32
Figure 18 Risk assessment module – fifth screen.....	32
Figure 19 Risk assessment module – sixth screen	32

List of tables

Table 1 Current temperature sum >100C.....	14
Table 2 Prevailing slope gradient.....	15
Table 3 Presence of stones and gravel in the topsoil.....	15
Table 4 Value of the texture factor characteristic of the soil.....	15
Table 5 Groundwater level.....	16
Table 6 Mechanical composition (physical clay - particles < 0.01 mm %)......	16
Table 7 Depth to root barrier.....	17
Table 8 Soil reaction value	17
Table 9 Humus content of the surface layer	17
Table 10 Land characteristics	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
Table 11 Soil Health Risk Assessment.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
Table 12 Gross margin calculation for current practices.....	20
Table 13 Gross margin calculation after risk mitigation practices	21
Table 14 Crop rotation scenario	24

Summary

This document reports on a of decision support tool (DST) for soil health business models and an overall update on its progress carried out under T 3.5: “Decision support tool for soil health business models“ in the framework of WP3 "Testing and development of a toolbox for incentives" under the NOVASOIL project.

Task 3.5 will work in close relation with WP4 to create a decision supporting tool for the incentive mechanism and new business models (i.e. supply chain contract, carbon market). The model uses both an assessment tool that is based on a fuzzy-logic approach for the estimation of soil health risk of cropping practices, and a linear programming model, that simulates farmers' economic behavior under the assumption of gross margin maximization being the main goal of farmers' actions.

The report presents structure and modules contained in the NOVASOIL DST for soil health business models. Also, it is presented the applied user-friendly architecture of the NOVASOIL DST and its design.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context of WP 3 objectives

The objective of the task T 3.5: “Decision support tool for soil health business models” is build a DST for soil health business models. To develop optimization tools managing information on soil health business models address the delivery of various ecosystem services and improved practices tailored to the needs of various stakeholders and land uses and policy decision makers. For that, WP3 will identify and optimize the different legal options according to the actors and the “package” of ecosystem services sought – but also the risks – relevance of payments for environmental services. We will take into account the different legal tools: contracts but also environmental obligations of legal framework for sustainable investments. Future texts from strategies such as certification will be taken into account

The tool is developed as a web-based digital tool and free-open access.

1.2 Connection with the other WPs

Connection with WP1: Indicators and definitions proposed in the framework have been considered for the NOVASOIL DST. Key actors interaction and needs and demands from case studies.

Connection with WP2: Lessons learned from Discrete Choice Experiments and list of main land practices management related soil health.

Connection with WP3: It will be used analysis applied and verified under tasks T3.1, T3.2, and T3.3. Based on the information from incentive mapping (task 3.1), information from the digital hub of knowledge (task 3.2) and the defined current and new incentives (task 3.3), several scenarios will be constructed to optimize the economic effect of the implementation of incentives related to improving soil health.

Connection with WP4: The DST will support the evaluation of the different policies effects on the soil health business models. The simulations can serve as a decision support tool for the development of soil health policies and help to foresee the effects of general changes of agricultural policies

Connection with WP5: T 3.5 will be shared with the audience, including the Communities of Practice in cooperation with WP5.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the document

Deliverable D3.6 Preliminary version on decision support tool for soil health business models aims to define the NOVASOIL digital support tool for soil health business models, which is part of T 3.5: "Decision support tool for soil health business models". It is presented as a preliminary framework of DST for soil health business models.

This document provides an overview of the main contents and features of the NOVASOIL DST according to the needs and demands and the potential indicators and features identified in previous activities carried out in the project.

1.4 Process of development

The complete development process of the digital tool involved several steps:

- 1) Selection and definition of the main elements of the digital tool.

In this first step, NBU presented its initial ideas for the digital tool at the plenary session in Munich. During the session, the tool's objective and potential users were reiterated to the partners, as well as its main functionalities and sections. Additionally, the integration of the knowledge hub was presented. Other tasks included drafting the structure, selecting service providers, developing graphic design and page titles, and creating a preliminary digital version of the DST for soil health business models.

This initial phase involved discussions on the tool's direction, whether it would be a set of locally executable tools or a web-based environment, as well as

potential functionalities for result visualization. It was agreed that developing a web-based environment for the tool, requiring only user registration, would be the most user-friendly approach.

2) Connection with other WPs

The second step aimed to identify the best way for other Work Packages (WPs) to contribute to the tool's development and determine the necessary content.

This step was carried out through virtual meetings and the plenary session in Sofia. During this session, partners contributed ideas and potential content improvements, also considering the results obtained from the analysis of the sector's needs and demands.

EVENOR and UNIPI supported the process of bilateral meetings to define the tool's final components and potential connections with the WPs.

3) Selection and discussion with the subcontracted entity

Once the main features of the digital tool were defined, the selection of the subcontracted entity responsible for the tool's development proceeded. NBU held numerous meetings with the selected entity to specifically define the tool's functionalities and its maintenance. Regarding the data of registered users, the security system for data privacy was discussed.

Preliminary digital version of the DST can be found on: <https://www.figma.com/proto/twaWv7Vhh0y4t6Unrpa8Wf/Novasoil-Tool?node-id=98-101&t=rZPbfPa7sLHJOcW5-1>

Password: under request

2 Conceptual framework

WP 3's aim is a toolbox development. It contains three major components (fig. 1). The final version of the first tool – digital hub of knowledge – was presented in D3.5 Report on final version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models (Nikolov et al. 2024) submitted in May 2024.

Digital tools for soil health business models are the second tool. It aims to help the selection of the most appropriate incentives based on the internal, external environment, and costs for implementation. The preliminary version of tools for analysis of the soil health business models was presented in D 3.3 (Nikolov et al., 2024).

The focus of this deliverable is the third tool – Decision support tools for soil health business models.

Figure 1. WP 3 digital toolbox

2.1 DST framework and connection between the tools

The goal of DST is to support the choose of the most appropriate soil health risk mitigation strategy taking into consideration the specific soil health risk, soil health risk mitigation activities and the costs for implementation (fig. 2).

The DST for soil health business models includes three main modules:

- Registration module;
- Risk assessment module;
- Optimisation module.

The user must make a registration to see they history and to perform new one.

Figure 2. NOVASOIL DST connection

All components of the tool will be tested with real data. Also, the tools will be presented to stakeholders and based on the feedback will be made correction if it is needed.

2.2 NOVASOIL DST description

The aim the included tools in NOVASOIL DST for soil health business models is to support the decision to implement new incentives in the farms taking into consideration the soil health risk specific environment and the implementation costs.

2.2.1 Registration module

This model aims to contain all initial socioeconomic data for the business model – registration and description of the business case – what is the business model, participants, roles, description of land, crops, rotation etc.

The DST needs registration log in and log out options. The users should provide mandatory and optional data to register and perform the further analysis.

The DST is GDPR compliant with NBU responsible body defined personal data, the purpose of data processing, transfer of data to third parties, duration of the data storage, etc. The policy will be accessible on the DST website.

Mandatory data

These type if data include:

- 1- Name
- 2- Region
- 3- Age
- 4- Sex
- 5- Level of education
- 6- Cultivated land (owned / land for rent)
- 7- Soil type
- 8- Number of people working:
 - a. Permanent (number):
 - b. Seasonal (number):
- 9- Crops - main and secondary, rotation
- 10- Livestock details (premise for the animals)
- 11- Machines owned (tractors, harvesters, equipment):
 - a. Owned:
 - b. Rented:

12- Buildings (storages, house - with approximate value)

Optional data

13- Subsidies received; did he has some experience with Rural development program, experience with other European programs

14- Certificates of production and of type...(do they have organic certificate, or they adjust to some supermarkets standards...)

15- What are the relations with the other stakeholders of the business model:

a. Formal (what type):

b. Informal:

2.2.2 Risk assessment module (RAM)

The business model needs the soil health risk must be estimated. In the frame of the DST we developed this module based on a fuzzy-logic approach for the estimation of soil health risk of cropping practices.

The backbone of the RAM tool stems from the soil indicators recommended by FAO and the indicators identified in NOVASOIL D1.1. This approach ensures wider and deeper evaluation of the analyzed risk at farm level in the context of local Soil Health business model.

For this, several questions have to be answered related with soil health. The approach used included answers to 12 questions related to soil health. Depending on the answers, which are structured according to different levels of restrictions L, the level of risk is determined. An option is chosen from drop down menu options to answer the questions. Depending on the answer the appropriate level is given (L).

The questions are:

Q1. $\Sigma T^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the period with average daily temperatures $>10^{\circ}\text{C}$

Table 1 Current temperature sum $>100\text{C}$

$\Sigma T^{\circ}>10^{\circ}\text{C}$	Levels of limitations L^{TS}
> 3600	L^{TS}_0
$3600 \quad \div \quad 3100$	L^{TS}_1
$3100 \quad \div \quad 2600$	L^{TS}_2
$2600 \quad \div \quad 1900$	L^{TS}_3
< 1900	L^{TS}_4

Source: own calculations

The farmer is asked to indicate the current temperature sum $>10^{\circ}\text{C}$ for his farm, which is then estimated according to the second column in the table.

Q2. Conditions of natural atmospheric humidification

Table 2. Assessment of natural atmospheric humidification

p-E _(VI-VIII) mm	Restriction levels L ^{WB}
> -100	L ^{WB} ₀
-100 ÷ -200	L ^{WB} ₁
-200 ÷ -300	L ^{WB} ₂
-300 ÷ -400	L ^{WB} ₃
< -400	L ^{WB} ₄

Source: own calculations

The farmer is asked to indicate the current conditions of natural atmospheric humidification for his farm, which is then estimated according to the second column in the table.

Q3. Prevailing slope gradient (%)

Table 3 Prevailing slope gradient

Prevailing slopes %	Levels of limitations L ^{SL}
< 2 or terraced areas	L ^{SL} ₀
2 ÷ 8	L ^{SL} ₁
8 ÷ 16	L ^{SL} ₂
16 ÷ 30	L ^{SL} ₃
> 30	L ^{SL} ₄

Source: own calculations

The farmer is asked to indicate the prevailing slope gradient for his farm, which is then to be estimated according to the second column in the table.

Q4. Topsoil stoniness (%)

Table 4 Presence of stones and gravel in the topsoil

Stones and gravel in % volume	Levels of limitations L ST
< 5	L ST ₀
5 ÷ 15	L ST ₁
15 ÷ 30	L ST ₂
30 ÷ 40	L ST ₃
> 40	L ST ₄

Source: own calculations

The farmer is required to indicate the presence of stones and gravel in the topsoil, which indicator is then to be assessed according to the second column in the table.

Q5. Texture coefficient

Table 5 Value of the texture factor characteristic of the soil

Texture coefficient	Levels of limitations L ^{TD}
< 1.3	L ^{TD} ₀
1.3 ÷ 1.5	L ^{TD} ₁
1.5 ÷ 2.0	L ^{TD} ₂
2.0 ÷ 2.5	L ^{TD} ₃
> 2.5	L ^{TD} ₄

Source: own calculations

The farmer is required to indicate the value of the texture factor characteristic of the soil on his farm, which is determined by the following approach. The farmer enters data on the content of physical clay - particles < 0.01 mm (%) in the lightest layer of the surface horizons (layers) (IB) and the content of physical clay - particles < 0.01 mm (%) in the lightest layer of the surface horizons (IA). Based on this data, the texture factor is calculated using the formula below and the restriction levels are determined.

$$Kt = \frac{IB}{IA}$$

IB - physical clay content – particles < 0.01 mm (%) in the heaviest layer of the subsurface horizons (layers);

IA - physical clay content – particles < 0.01 mm (%) in the lightest layer of surface horizons (layers).

Q6. Groundwater level (cm)

Table 6 Groundwater level

Groundwater level cm	Levels of limitations L ^{GWT}
> 300	L ^{GWT} ₀
300 ÷ 200	L ^{GWT} ₁
200 ÷ 100	L ^{GWT} ₂
100 ÷ 50	L ^{GWT} ₃
< 50	L ^{GWT} ₄

Source: own calculations

The farmer is required to indicate the groundwater level, which is then assessed according to the second column in the table.

Q7. Soil fertility data

Table 7 Mechanical composition (physical clay - particles < 0.01 mm %)

Physical clay %	Levels of limitations L ^{TX}
< 10	L ^{TX} ₄
10 ÷ 20	L ^{TX} ₃
20 ÷ 30	L ^{TX} ₂
30 ÷ 45	L ^{TX} ₁
45 ÷ 60	L ^{TX} ₀

60	÷	75	L^{TX}_1
		> 75	L^{TX}_2

Source: own calculations

The farmer is asked to indicate the physical clay content of the soil profile, which is then estimated according to the second column in the table.

Q8. Root space (depth to root barrier cm)

Table 8 Depth to root barrier

Depth to root barrier cm	Levels of limitations L^{RS}
> 130	L^{RS}_0
130 ÷ 100	L^{RS}_1
100 ÷ 80	L^{RS}_2
80 ÷ 50	L^{RS}_3
< 50	L^{RS}_4

Source: own calculations

The farmer is asked to indicate the depth at which a barrier to the development of the plant root system occurs, which indicator is to be assessed according to the second column in the table.

Q9. Soil reaction (pH measured in aqueous suspension)

Table 9 Soil reaction value

Soil reaction – pH in H ₂ O	Levels of limitations L^{PH}
< 5.0	L^{PH}_4
5.0 ÷ 6.0	L^{PH}_3
6.0 ÷ 6.5	L^{PH}_2
6.5 ÷ 7.3	L^{PH}_0
7.3 ÷ 8.6	L^{PH}_1
> 8.6	not evaluated

Source: own calculations

The farmer is asked to indicate the soil reaction value to be estimated according to the second column in the table.

Q10. Humus content

Table 10 Humus content of the surface layer

Humus content %	Levels of limitations L^{HC}
> 3.0	L^{HC}_0
3.0 ÷ 2.5	L^{HC}_1
2.5 ÷ 2.0	L^{HC}_2
2.0 ÷ 1.0	L^{HC}_3
< 1.0	L^{HC}_4

Source: own calculations

The farmer is asked to indicate the humus content of the surface layer of the soil profile, which is estimated according to the second column in the table.

Q11. Soil salinity and/or alkalinity

Table 11 Estimation of salinity and/or alkalinity of soils

Water soluble salts (%)	L ^{SA}	Exchanged Na (% от Т)	L ^{AL}
< 0.3	L ^{SA} ₀	< 5	L ^{AL} ₀
0.3 ÷ 0.5	L ^{SA} ₁	5 ÷ 10	L ^{AL} ₁
0.5 ÷ 0.8	L ^{SA} ₂	10 ÷ 15	L ^{AL} ₂
0.8 ÷ 1.0	L ^{SA} ₃	15 ÷ 20	L ^{AL} ₃
> 1.0	L ^{SA} ₄	> 20	L ^{AL} ₄
The final score L ^{SAAL} = of the more restrictive than L ^{SA} и L ^{AL}			

Source: own calculations

The farmer is asked to indicate the salinity and/or alkalinity of the soil profile, which is estimated according to the second column in the table.

Q12. Soil contamination with heavy metals and toxic elements

Table 12 Assessment of soil contamination

DSC leading pollutant %	Restriction levels L ^{CO}
< 0	L ^{CO} ₀
0 ÷ 30	L ^{CO} ₁
30 ÷ 65	L ^{CO} ₂
65 ÷ 100	L ^{CO} ₃
>100	L ^{CO} ₄

Source: own calculations

To determine the degree of soil contamination (DSC) with the individual soil pollutant /SP/, the farmer has to use an algorithm shown below on Equation 6:

$$DSC = 100(MCSP - PC)/(MPC - PC) \quad (6)$$

Where:

- DSC - Degree of soil contamination with SP (%).
- MCSP - Measured concentration of SP (mg/kg).
- PC - Protective concentration of SP (mg/kg).
- MPC - Maximum permissible concentration of SP (mg/kg).

After the farmers goes through all 12 questions it is collected L estimation for all questions. That can be summarized as:

Table 13 Soil Health Risk Assessment

Soil class	Units	Criteria
S ₁ Very good soil	(1)	Land units that:
	(2)	have no restrictions or have up to 5 L ₁ restrictions
S ₂ Good soil	(1)	Land units that:
	(2)	have up to 5 L ₁ restrictions or have up to 4 restrictions L ₂

S ₃	Average good soil	(1) (2)	Land units that: have up to 4 restrictions L ₂ or have up to 3 restrictions L ₃
N ₁	Poor soil	(1) (2)	Land units that: have up to 3 restrictions L ₃ or have up to 1 restrictions L ₄
N ₂	Unsuitable soil	(1) (2)	Land units that: have up to 4 restrictions L ₃ or have up to 1 restrictions L ₄

Source: own calculations

Placing the lands in the above-mentioned classes allows making recommendations for improving soil health (table 14).

Table 14 Recommendations for soil health improvement

Land classes	Leading limiting factor	Use	Improvement measures
S ₁	Without limitations	For all crops in the given climate	Fertilization and irrigation, bioprotective belts
S ₂	Some have high groundwater levels	For all crops for which there are climatic conditions - cereals, root crops and tubers, perennial fodder, essential oil and medicinal, technical, fruit, berry crops	Fertilization, drainage (if necessary), amelioration
S ₃	Stony, erosion, light mechanical composition, high level of groundwater, unfavourable soil reaction	Cereals, vegetable crops, fodder, lavender, walnuts, cherries, vineyards, pastures, forests	Stone removal, fertilization, land reclamation, anti-erosion measures, weeding, afforestation
N ₁	Shallow hard rock, erosion, poor in nutrients, acidic reaction or high carbonate content	Potatoes, tobacco, lavender, raspberries, herbs, pastures, forests	Anti-erosion measures, fertilizing, weeding, afforestation, terracing, horizontal processing

N ₂	Shallow hard rock, erosion, poor in nutrients, acidic reaction or high carbonate content	Grasslands, protected areas around settlements, forests	Anti-erosion measures, preservation of forests, afforestation, terracing
----------------	--	---	--

2.2.3 Optimisation module

Selection of incentives and practices for soil health

The result of the process in RAM module is the definition of the soil health, which have to be visible for the farmer.

After the estimation of the soil health risk a list with incentives and practices that he can use to mitigate the soil health risk.

- The farmer can see a list with incentives from D3.1.
- The farmer can see list with practices.

Risk mitigation

To estimate the risk mitigation the Gross Margin (GM) will be used.

To calculate the GM the farmer must be asked a list of questions for **every crop** on the farm. Every row from table 2 must be answered by the farmer.

Table 15 Gross margin calculation for current practices

Crop type:				
Income	Measure (kg, l, ...) per ha	Yield	Price	Total
			EUR	EUR
Main product				
Side product 1	kg			
Side product 2	kg			
Subsidy	EUR			
Total income				
Vatable Costs		Quantity	Price	Value
			EUR	EUR
Seeds	kg			
	kg			
Fertilizers	kg			

	kg			
	kg			
Plant protection	l			
	l			
	l			
Labor				
Manual labour	Person days			
Harvesting	Person days			
Marketing	EUR			
Packing	EUR			
Contracts				
Ploughing	EUR			
Disking	EUR			
Harvest	EUR			
Sowing	EUR			
Fertilizing and spraying	EUR			
Other				
Equipment Rental				
Irrigation	M ³			
Other costs				
Fuel	l			
Total Variable Costs				

Source: own calculations

GM= Total income – Total variable costs

Application of risk mitigation brings some change in income and costs related with GM calculation.

The farmer has to be asked the same set of questions after the application of risk mitigation practices for **every crop**.

Calculation of GM after risk mitigation practices is presented in table 2.

Table 16 Gross margin calculation after risk mitigation practices

Crop type:				
Income	Measure (kg, l, ...) per ha	Yield	Price	Total
			EUR	EUR
Main product				

Side product 1	kg			
Side product 2	kg			
Subsidy	EUR			
Total income				
Vatable Costs		Quantity	Price	Value
			EUR	EUR
Seeds	kg			
	kg			
Fertilizers	kg			
	kg			
	kg			
Plant protection	l			
	l			
	l			
Labor				
Manual labor	Person days			
Harvesting	Person days			
Marketing	EUR			
Packing	EUR			
Contracts				
Plowing	EUR			
Disking	EUR			
Harvest	EUR			
Sowing	EUR			
Fertilizing and spraying	EUR			
Other				
Equipment Rental				
Irrigation	M ³			
Other costs				
Fuel	l			
Total Variable Costs				

Source: own calculations

Linear optimization

Linear optimization plays a crucial role in economics, offering powerful tools for solving complex problems. Linear programming, a branch of applied mathematics, focuses on minimizing or maximizing linear cost functions subject to linear constraints. This approach is particularly useful in production planning (Schulze, 1998). For the optimization, it is necessary to derive a

function to find a minimum or a maximum. It is also necessary to determine the quantitative constraints of the model.

If the problem has m variables and n constraints, the standard form of the linear optimization problem may be represented as:

$$\text{Maximize } \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ji} x_i \leq b_j, \quad j=1 \dots m$$

$$x_i \geq 0, \quad i=1 \dots n$$

The problem may have three possible categories: Infeasible, Unbounded and Optimal Solution. Optimal solution means the function achieves a unique minimum (or maximum) value.

The simplex method, along with its variants like the revised simplex method and network simplex method, has been the primary algorithm for solving linear programming problems efficiently over the past 50 years. The simplex method consists of two main phases. The first phase involves finding a feasible solution, which is often straightforward for small or certain larger problems, sometimes using a trivial solution like $x=0$. In the second phase, the simplex method iteratively improves the function by adjusting variables in a manner that increases one while decreasing another, leading to an overall enhancement in the function. A large advantage of the linear optimization problem is that in the last few decades it has been computerized and there exists software that can solve such problems.

When it comes to linear optimization of GM, the function can be represented as:

$$\text{Maximize } GM = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_i GM_i,$$

Where

Q_i - is the quantity of the land with crop i ;

GM_i - is the gross margin per ha for crop i .

This function is subject to several type of constraints:

- i. Constraints for the land
- ii. Constraints for the crop rotation
- iii. Constraints for the labor
- iv. Constraints for the irrigation

Schulze, M.A. (1998). Linear Programming for Optimization.

Based on the collected information defined above a linear optimization can be done. The optimization objective is GM of the farm. The quantity of land with a single crop is the optimization solution.

For that purpose, we need the following table:

Table 17 Crop rotation scenario

Type of crops	Total	Wheat	Maize	Sunflower	Barley	Rye	Oats	Vegetables
Number of crops		1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Quantity hectares	100	50	0	0	0	0	0	50
Revenue per hectare								
Average yield per hectare		470	600	200	460			3500
Price per unit		0.3	0.3	0.6	0.29			0.6
Income per hectare of main production		141	180	120	133.4	0	0	2100
Incentive (Subsidy) per hectare		30	30	30	30			31
Quantity of by-product per hectare								
By-product price per unit								
Income from secondary production		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total revenue		8550	0	0	0	0	0	106550
Cost per hectare								
Seed quantity per hectare		30	2	0.5	22			0.1
Price per unit quantity		0.32	5.5	20	0.38			200
Seed costs		9.6	11	10	8.36	0	0	20
Fertiliser 1 quantity per hectare		1	1	1	1			2
Fertiliser 1 price per unit		33	35	17	32			12
Cost of fertiliser 1		33	35	17	32	0	0	24
Fertiliser 2 quantity per hectare								30
Fertiliser 2 price per unit								1.4
Cost of fertiliser 2		0	0	0	0	0	0	42
Fertiliser 3 quantity per hectare								3
Fertiliser 3 cost per unit								6.25
Cost of fertiliser 3		0	0	0	0	0	0	18.75
Labour 1 person/day per ha								
Labour 1 price per person day								
Total Labour 1		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Labour 2 person/day per ha		1	1	1	1			0.8
Labour 2 price per person day		6	12	11	6.5			35
Total Labour 2		6	12	11	6.5	0	0	28
Labour 3 person/day per ha								
Labour 3 price per person day								
Total Labour 3		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fuel quantity per hectare		6.5	8	8	6.5			40
Fuel price per unit		2.66	2.66	2.66	2.66			2.66
Total fuel		17.29	21.28	21.28	17.29	0	0	106.4

Number of people in permanent labour								
Price per hectare of permanent labour								
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seasonal labour in man-days								17
Price per day of seasonal labour								20
		0	0	0	0	0	0	340
Irrigation quantity per hectare								90
Irrigation price per unit								1.6
		0	0	0	0	0	0	144
Total variable costs		3 294.5	0	0	0	0	0	36 157.5

Source: own calculations

Limitations' definitions

A set of limitation for linear optimization will apply. These limitations come in 2 ways:

1. They are preset in the software
2. The farmer may set some of the limitations

3. Design of the DTs

The NOVASOIL DST for soil health business models contains three modules:

- Registration;
- Risk assessment;
- Optimisation.

3.1 Registration module (RM)

In terms of registration, the user should complete information about:

- Names
- Age group: 18-29; 30-39; 40-49; 50-59; 60-69; +70;
- Gender: female; male; no binary; I prefer not to answer;
- User: farmer; policy maker; researcher; industry and supply chain actors; NGOs and civil society; landowners; consumers; other – specify.
- Country:
- e-mail
- password and re-enter the password.

3.2 Risk assessment module (RAM)

In this module the user could evaluate the soil in 9 easy steps. Figures XX present the process for evaluation.

Figure 3 RAM first page

Figure 4 RAM soil L-level

novasoil

Search ...

Nikolay Buchkov

Menu

- Soil Calculator

Others

- Help Center
- Provide Feedback
- Settings

Logout

Conditions of natural atmospheric humidification

Assessment of natural atmospheric humidification

> -100

-100 ÷ -200

-200 ÷ -300

-300 ÷ -400

< -400

Next

Figure 5 RAM - natural atmospheric humidification

novasoil

Search ...

Nikolay Buchkov

Menu

- Soil Calculator

Others

- Help Center
- Provide Feedback
- Settings

Logout

Choose the predominant slope percentage of the terrain

Collect soil samples from various locations within the area to get a representative sample.

< 2

2 - 8

8 - 16

16 - 30

> 30

Next

Figure 6 RAM - predominant slope

novasoil

Search ...

Nikolay Buchkov

Menu

- Soil Calculator

Others

- Help Center
- Provide Feedback
- Settings

Logout

Choose the stony layer of the soil

Collect soil samples from various locations within the area to get a representative sample.

< 5

5 - 15

15 - 30

30 - 40

> 40

Next

Figure 7 RAM – stony layer

novasoi

Menu

- Soil Calculator**

Others

- Help Center
- Provide Feedback
- Settings

Logout

Search ...

Nikolay Buchkov

Choose the groundwater level

Collect soil samples from various locations within the area to get a representative sample.

> 300	300 - 200	200 - 100
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
100 - 50	< 50	
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

Next

Figure 8 RAM - groundwater level

novasoi

Menu

- Soil Calculator**

Others

- Help Center
- Provide Feedback
- Settings

Logout

Search ...

Nikolay Buchkov

Choose the root zone

Collect soil samples from various locations within the area to get a representative sample.

> 130	130 - 100	100 - 80
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
80 - 50	< 50	
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

Next

Figure 9 RAM - root zone

novasoi

Menu

- Soil Calculator**

Others

- Help Center
- Provide Feedback
- Settings

Logout

Search ...

Nikolay Buchkov

Choose the soil pH (reaction)

Collect soil samples from various locations within the area to get a representative sample.

< 5.0	5.0 - 6.0	6.0 - 6.5
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6.5 - 7.3	7.3 - 8.6	> 8.6
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Calculate

Figure 10 RAM - Soil pH

Very good Soils !
Collect soil samples from various locations within the area to get a representative sample.

Types	Units	Criteria
S1 Very good Soil	(1) (2)	Land units that have no restrictions or have up to 5 L ₁ restrictions
S2 Good Soil	(1) (2)	Land units that have up to 5 L ₁ restrictions or have up to 4 restrictions L ₂
S3 Average good Soil	(1) (2)	Land units that have up to 4 restrictions L ₂ or have up to 3 restrictions L ₃
N1 Poor Soil	(1) (2)	Land units that have up to 3 restrictions L ₃ or have up to 1 restrictions L ₄
N2 Unsuitable Soil	(1) (2)	Land units that have up to 4 restrictions L ₃ or have up to 1 restrictions L ₄

See Incentives

Figure 11 RAM - result

Without Limitations
Collect soil samples from various locations within the area to get a representative sample.

Types	Usage	Actions for improvements
S1 Without limitations	For all crops in the given climate	Fertilization and irrigation, bioprotective belts
S2 Some have high groundwater levels	For all crops for which there are climatic conditions - cereals, root crops and tubers, perennial fodder, essential oil and medicinal, technical, fruit, berry crops	Fertilization, drainage (if necessary), amelioration
S3 Stony, erosion, light mechanical composition, high level of groundwater, unfavorable soil reaction	Cereals, vegetable crops, fodder, lavender, walnuts, cherries, vineyards, pastures, forests	Stone removal, fertilization, land reclamation, anti-erosion measures, weeding, afforestation
N1 Shallow hard rock, erosion, poor in nutrients, acidic reaction or high carbonate content	Potatoes, tobacco, lavender, raspberries, herbs, pastures, forests	Anti-erosion measures, fertilizing, weeding, afforestation, terracing, horizontal processing
N2 Shallow hard rock, erosion, poor in nutrients, acidic reaction or high carbonate content	Grazing lands, protected areas around settlements, forests	Anti-erosion measures, preservation of forests, afforestation, terracing

Next

Figure 12 RAM recommendations

3.3 Optimisation module (OM)

The optimisation module includes risk mitigation part. The figures 5 – 10 show the steps needed to be performed this analysis.

Total size of land in hectares

1: How much is your land size

2: Which period does this data cover

3: Select Crop Types

CULTURES	FUSED SURFACE	TRENCH	SECOND CULTURE	GREEN FERTILIZATION
1. Cereals				
1.1 Cereal Crops				
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Soft Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="radio"/> Durum Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="radio"/> Soft Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="radio"/> Soft Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="radio"/> Soft Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="radio"/> Soft Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="radio"/> Soft Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="radio"/> Soft Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="radio"/> Soft Wheat	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 13 OM – first screen

Before Risk Mitigation
 Data before applying RM incentives

LEQUME:

Income	Measure (kg, l.) per ha	Yield	Price	Total
Main Product			EUR	EUR
+				
Main Product				
Side Product 1	kg/ha			
Side Product 2	kg/ha			
Subsidy	EUR			
Total Income				
+				
Variable Costs		Quantity	Price	Total
			EUR	EUR
Seeds	kg/ha			EUR
	kg/ha			
Fertilized	kg/ha			
	kg/ha			
	kg/ha			
Plant Protection	l/ha			
	l/ha			
	l/ha			
Labor				
Manual Labor	Personal Days			
Marketing	EUR			
Packing	EUR			
Contracts				
Plowing	EUR			
Disking	EUR			
Harvest	EUR			
Swing	EUR			
Fertilizing and spraying	EUR			
Other	EUR			
Equipment Rental				
Irrigation	M ³			
+				
Other costs	M ³			
Fuel	l			
Harvest	EUR			
Swing	EUR			
Fertilizing and spraying	EUR			
Other	EUR			
Equipment Rental				
Irrigation	M ³			
+				
Other costs				
Fuel	l			
+				
Total Variable Costs				

Figure 14 OM – second screen

After Risk Mitigation
Data after applying RM incentives

LEGUME:

Income	Measure (kg, l) per ha	Yield	Price EUR	Total EUR
+				
Main Product				
Side Product 1	kg/ha			
Side Product 2	kg/ha			
Subsidy	EUR			
Total Income				
+				
Variable Costs		Quantity	Price EUR	Total EUR
Seeds	kg/ha			EUR
Fertilized	kg/ha			EUR
Plant Protection	l/ha			EUR
Other	l/ha			EUR
Laber				
Manual labor	Personal Days			
Marketing				EUR
Packing				EUR
Contracts				
Plowing				EUR
Disking				EUR
Harvest				EUR
Swing				EUR
Fertilizing and spraying				EUR
Other				EUR
Equipment Rental				
Irrigation	M ²			
+				
Other costs				
Fuel	l			
Harvest				EUR
Swing				EUR
Fertilizing and spraying				EUR
Other				EUR
Equipment Rental				
Irrigation	M ²			
+				
Other costs				
Fuel	l			
+				
Total Variable Costs				

Next

Figure 15 OM – third screen

GM Per Hectar Overview

1: GM Before Risk Mitigation

Crop Type	Corn	Sunflower	Barley	Vegetables
Income per hectare	474	0	0	0
Expense per hectare	274	0	0	0
GM Per Hectar	200	0	0	0

If you want to calculate gross margin based on your own input, please input how hectares of any crop you would like to plant. Feel free to skip this step.

Hectares:	Corn	Sunflower	Barley	Vegetables
0	0	0	0	0
GM:	0	0	0	0
Total GM:	0	0	0	0

2: GM After Risk Mitigation

Crop Type	Corn	Sunflower	Barley	Vegetables
Income per hectare	474	0	0	0
Expense per hectare	274	0	0	0
GM Per Hectar	200	0	0	0

If you want to calculate gross margin based on your own input, please input how hectares of any crop you would like to plant. Feel free to skip this step.

Hectares:	Corn	Sunflower	Barley	Vegetables
0	0	0	0	0
GM:	0	0	0	0
Total GM:	0	0	0	0

Calculate Optimal GM **Download**

Figure 16 OM – forth screen

Limitation
Set Limitations when calculating optimal GM

Minimum land planted with

Maximum land planted with

How much percentage should be with row crops?

How much percentage should be with solid crops?

Crop variety of at least / crops

Calculate

Figure 17 OM – fifth screen

Optimal GM
This is the optimal way to use your land based on your specifications

1: GM Before Risk Mitigation

Crop Type	Corn	Sunflower	Barley	Vegetables
Income per hectare	474	0	0	0
Expense per hectare	274	0	0	0
GM Per Hectar	200	0	0	0

If you want to calculate gross margin based on your own input, please input how hectares of any crop you would like to plant. Feel free to skip this step

	Corn	Sunflower	Barley	Vegetables
Hectares: <input type="text" value="20"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
GM:	1500	1200	15	0
Total GM:	24230			

2: GM After Risk Mitigation

Crop Type	Corn	Sunflower	Barley	Vegetables
Income per hectare	474	0	0	0
Expense per hectare	274	0	0	0
GM Per Hectar	200	0	0	0

Below you will find the optimal hectares to plant on each crop based on the limitations

	Corn	Sunflower	Barley	Vegetables
Hectares: <input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
GM:	1500	1200	15	0
Total GM:	24230			

Finish

Figure 18 OM – sixth screen

4 Conclusions

Deliverable 3.6 presents the preliminary version of the NOVASOIL DST for soil health business models. In the first part of the DST, based on information processed through the fuzzy logic approach, the risk related to soil health is

assessed based on indicators recommended by FAO and used in the soil monitoring process (NOVASOIL D1.1). On this basis, the tool envisages the provision of recommendations on certain practices aimed at improving soil health. In the second part DST produce suggesting optimal solutions based on different scenarios for simulation farmers' economic behaviour under the assumption of gross margin maximization. Implementing the limitations in the optimization module can simulate also how policy changes can have an impact on soil health business models.

The functionality is described based on three modules: registration module, risk assessment module, and optimisation module. In addition, it is presented the design of NOVASOIL DST.

The three modules will be tested and improved until the DST final version (M32) based on the feedback received. There improvements may be based on the introduction of new variables for soil health or new incentives/policies.

This deliverable sets the foundation for D3.9 – Report on final version on decision support tool for soil health business models due in M32.

Resources

1. Nikolov D., Tzvetanova E., Boevsky I., Banov M., Kostenarov K., Todorova K. (2024) Deliverable D 3.5 Report on final version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models
2. Nikolov D., Tzvetanova E., Boevsky I., Banov M., Kostenarov K., Todorova K. (2024) Deliverable D 3.3 Preliminary version of tools for analysis of the soil health business models
3. Clickable demo version of the NOVASOIL DST is available at: <https://www.figma.com/proto/twaWv7Vhh0y4t6Unrpa8Wf/Novasoil-Tool?node-id=98-101&t=rZPbfPa7sLHJOcW5-1>

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank the EU for funding, in the frame of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement GA 101091268. The document reflects only the author's view. The Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

